

Incorporation of Fibrous/Particulate Bioglass in Soft Matrices for Soft Tissue Applications

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ABSTRACT

Application of bioactive glasses in orthopedic and dental application, as well as bone tissue engineering gained a great interest in the last 50 years since its discovery by Hench et al. in 1971 [1]. Most frequently studied and well documented system for bone filling materials, dental application and bone implants are the bioglass compositions 455S (45% SiO₂, 24.5% Na₂O and CaO, 6% P₂O₅ by wt.) and 13-93 (53% SiO₂, 20% CaO, 12% K₂O, 6% Na₂O, 5% MgO, 4% P₂O₅). Recently boron containing glasses attracted attention for applications for beyond bone and teeth: soft tissue applications including wound healing are also studied. Bioactive borate glasses show 5 times faster biodegradation and better bioactivity. Unlike the 45S5 silicate bioactive glass, they transform to hydroxyapatite (HA) completely. This feature originates from less stable structure of boron containing glasses. The ions, such as B, Na and Ca, which release into surrounding area have been observed to contribute to regulation of the wound healing process [2], [3], [4].

To provide an optimum environment for creating new tissue, biomaterials have to allow transportation of nutrition and oxygen between cells and extracellular matrix. To achieve this, polymer matrices such as polylactic acid are widely used because of its low cost, low energy required during production process. They are also easily thermally processible, nontoxic for human body and possess Food and Drug Administration approval. However, the polymers by themselves are insufficient in providing required mechanical strength, chemical reactivity, biocompatibility and bioactivity to mimic natural tissue. Their mechanical properties must be improved and optimized, and additional bioactivity has to be provided by other components. Borate glasses are candidate for preparation of a composite material which could provide temporary support for creating new tissue formation [5].

In my future work, I will produce borate glass with Zn as a therapeutic ion via conventional glass melting process. Powder form of borate glass will act as a reinforcement component for composite materials. Thermally induced phase separation method (TIPS) will be used for scaffold preparation by providing convenient scaffold architecture including amount, size, and shape of porosity, and freeze drying will be applied for removing the solvent from scaffold. After morphology and porosity analysis, mechanical properties will be measured. Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) solution will be prepared for biodegradation study, bioactivity test will be carried out with the use of a simulated body fluid (SBF), and evaluated by the change of the SBF chemical composition by ICP OES.

Keywords: Bioglass, soft matrice, soft tissue.

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